

Young and Eyre (*loc. cit.*), however, observed² that the product of the oxidation of benzylidene-thiosemicarbazone with ferric chloride consisted entirely of a thiodiazole derivative together with a trace of a higher melting alkali soluble product which they suspected to be a mercaptotriazole.

In the present work Young and Eyre's researches have been followed on an extensive scale taking a large number of thiosemicarbazones, but in no case could we trace the formation of a mercaptotriazole. Our next attempt was to find out a suitable oxidising agent with which the formation of the much expected mercaptotriazoles might be possible and the oxidising agent which answered our purpose has now been found in hydrogen peroxide.

The oxidation of the thiosemicarbazones with hydrogen peroxide takes place more easily and energetically than that with ferric chloride: in the latter case no reaction appears to take place in the cold, whereas the thio-compounds are oxidised by aqueous or alcoholic hydrogen peroxide even in the cold and in some cases the reaction is so violent that it becomes necessary to cool the reaction mixture during the addition of the oxidising agent (see Experimental part). The product is generally a disulphide of a mercaptotriazole, for instance (IX),

In one or two experiments there has also been obtained a substance which is free from sulphur and which may have been derived from the disulphide (Busch and Bauer, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 1067), as the result of further oxidation, the sulphur being eliminated as sulphur dioxide. The formation of the sulphur free compound (formula X), can be checked by careful addition of the calculated quantity of hydrogen peroxide and by allowing the temperature not to rise too high during addition.

It is now evident from the behaviour of the benzylidene-thiosemicarbazones towards hydrogen peroxide that they can react in either of the two possible stereoisomeric forms in presence of a suitable oxidising agent.

Hitherto we have only dealt with the two possible forms of compounds that can be derived from the two stereoisomeric forms of

aldehyde-thiosemicarbazones. Leaving aside the question of stereo-isomerism the oxidation may be supposed to proceed in an entirely different way leading to the formation of a thiodiazole (formula XI).

Such a reaction is not possible so long as the azomethane group is present, the hydrogen atom of which is extremely reactive (Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1679; Wedekind, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 444; Young, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 224; Busch and Walther, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1360). The reaction, therefore, takes the course as represented by formula (V) or (VI).

It was next thought that if the reactive hydrogen atom could be avoided as in the case of the ketone-thiosemicarbazones the reaction might be expected to proceed in the manner just described. To achieve this end several acetone-thiosemicarbazones were oxidised with hydrogen peroxide. The product of oxidation consists, as we expected, of thiodiazole derivatives different from those represented by formula (VII).

Thus we find that acetone-thiosemicarbazones can react with oxidising agents similarly as substituted arylthiourea which, as has been shown by Hector (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1177; 1892, 25, 1578) are oxidised by hydrogen peroxide to thiodiazole derivatives (formula XII).

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxidation of Thiosemicarbazones with Ferric Chloride

5 *Phenyl 2 amino 1 3 4 thiodiazole* —Benzylidene thiosemicarbazone was oxidised with ferric chloride according to the direction of Young and Eyre (*loc cit*) and the product consisted exclusively of 5 phenyl 2 amino 1 3 4 thiodiazole hydrochloride (m p 213°-214°) No trace of a substance of higher melting point as described by these authors could be obtained even by altering the condition of the reaction

5 *Styryl-2 amino 1 3 4-thiodiazole*

Cinnamylidene thiosemicarbazone was oxidised as before in aqueous suspension. The colourless solution obtained on heating the mixture for 10 mins did not deposit any crystals on cooling. The free base was precipitated along with ferrous hydroxide by ammonia, and from the solid residue the base was extracted with alcohol from which crystals separated on cooling. Recrystallised from alcohol it melts at 260°-261° (Found N 20.72 C₁₀H₉N₃S requires N, 20.68 per cent)

5-*Salicyl 2 amino 1 3 4 thiodiazole* —The oxidation was carried out as before with salicylidene 4 phenylthiosemicarbazone when a black solid product was obtained. The colour was partly removed by washing with ether and benzene. Crystallised from benzene with the addition of animal charcoal it formed white crystals (m p 190°-191° (Found N, 15.57 C₁₄H₁₁ON₃S requires N, 15.51 per cent))

5 *m Nitrophenyl-2-amido 1 3 4 thiodiazole* —It was obtained from the oxidation of *m* nitrobenzylidene 4 phenylthiosemicarbazone. The insoluble product was filtered from the mother liquor and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow rectangles, (m p 249°-250° (Found N, 18.82 C₁₄H₁₀O₂N₄S requires N, 18.79 per cent))

Acetyl Derivative —The above thiodiazole was heated with acetic anhydride for 10 mins. On cooling crystals separated which were recrystallised from acetic acid, (m p 246°. (Found : N, 16.62 C₁₆H₁₃O₂N₄S requires N, 16.47 per cent.))

5-p-Toluidino-2-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole.—Benzylidene-4 *p* tolylthiosemicarbazone (m.p. 165°) was oxidised in alcoholic solution. On cooling white crystals of the thiodiazole were obtained. Crystallised from alcohol in needles it melts at 198°-199°. (Found : N, 15·94. C₁₆H₁₅N₃S requires N, 15·73 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative.—It was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 155°. (Found : S, 10·61. C₁₇H₁₅ON₃S requires S, 10·35 per cent.).

5-p-Nitrophenyl-2-p-toluidino-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole.—Prepared from the oxidation of *p*-nitrobenzylidene-4-*p*-tolylthiosemicarbazone (m.p. 201-202°). After heating for 10 mins. the alcoholic solution became colourless and from the solution on cooling crystals were obtained which when crystallised from acetic acid melt at 197°-198°. (Found : N, 17·82. C₁₈H₁₅O₂N₄S requires N, 17·84 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative.—Prepared in the usual way it crystallises from alcohol in almost white needles, m.p. 243°. (Found : N, 15·96. C₁₇H₁₄O₃N₄S requires N, 15·81 per cent.).

5-Styryl-2-p-toluidino-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole.—It was obtained by oxidising cinnamylidene-4-*p*-tolylthiosemicarbazone. The water insoluble product was crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow rectangles, m.p. 184°. (Found : N, 14·16. C₁₇H₁₅N₃S requires N, 14·34 per cent.).

5-Phenyl-2-allylamino-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole.—It was prepared by oxidising benzylidene-4-allylthiosemicarbazone. The oily product formed which was insoluble in water was then treated with steam and allowed to stand overnight when it solidified to a crystalline mass. This was crystallised from alcohol in white plates, m.p. 114°-115°. (Found : N, 19·35. C₁₁H₁₁N₃S requires N 19·25 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative.—Prepared in the usual way and crystallised from acetic acid in white rectangles it melts at 120°. (Found : N, 16·35. C₁₃H₁₃ON₃S requires N, 16·21 per cent.).

5-m-Nitrophenyl-2-allylamino-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole.—On heating the *m*-nitrobenzylidene-4-allylthiosemicarbazone with the oxidising agent in alcoholic solution for 15 mins. and cooling the solution, the thiodiazole separated out. Crystallised from alcohol in white prisms with a faint yellow tinge it melts at 170°-171°. (Found : N, 21·58. C₁₁H₁₀O₂N₄S requires N, 21·37 per cent.).

5-p-Nitrophenyl-2-m-toluidino-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole.—The separated solid obtained from the oxidation of *p*-nitrobenzylidene-4-*m*-tolyl

thiosemicarbazone (m.p. 192°) was crystallised from acetic acid in deep yellow plates, m.p. 257°. (Found: N, 18·21. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17·94 per cent.).

5-Phenyl-2-m-toluidino-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—The oily resinous mass obtained by oxidising benzylidene-4-*m*-tolylthiosemicarbazone (m.p. 160°) was subjected to steam distillation and cooled; the solid mass obtained was dissolved in alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. On cooling crystals appeared which were recrystallised from benzene in white plates, m.p. 176°. (Found: 66·2°C., $H_{11}N_4S$ requires N, 15·73 per cent.).

5-m-Nitrophenyl-2-o-toluidino-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—It was prepared by oxidising *m*-nitrobenzylidene-4-*o*-tolylthiosemicarbazone (m.p. 219°) and crystallised from pyridine in light yellow needles, m.p. 247°-248°. (Found: N, 17·82. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17·94 per cent.).

5-m-Nitrophenyl-2-methylamino-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—Prepared from *m*-nitrobenzylidene-4-methylthiosemicarbazone. Crystals which separated from the aqueous solution on cooling were crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 23·85. $C_9H_8O_2N_4S$ requires N, 23·72 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative.—Obtained by heating the thiodiazole with acetic anhydride for 15 mins. and crystallised from pyridine in white plates, m.p. 225°-226°. (Found: N, 20·14. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 20·14 per cent.).

Methyl derivative.—It was prepared by heating the above thiodiazole with methyl iodide in a sealed tube at 100° for three hours. On cooling crystals of the product separated which were crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 209°. (Found: N, 22·52. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22·40 per cent.).

5-p-Nitrophenyl-2-methylamino-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—By oxidising *p*-nitrobenzylidene-4-methylthiosemicarbazone (m. p. 235°) the thiodiazole was obtained as a solid mass insoluble in water. Crystallised from pyridine it forms yellow needles, m.p. 262°. (Found: N, 23·83. $C_9H_8O_2N_4S$ requires N, 23·72 per cent.).

Its *acetyl derivative* was obtained in the usual way and crystallised from pyridine in white plates, m. p. 279°. (Found: S, 11·6%. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_4S$ requires S, 11·51 per cent.).

Its *methyl derivative* was prepared by heating the thiodiazole with methyl iodide as before. Crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles it melts at 203°. (Found: N, 22·37. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22·40 per cent.).

The *o*-nitrobenzylidene-4-*m*-xylylthiosemicarbazone was suspended in alcohol and oxidised as before with the required quantity of peroxide. The cold solution was filtered from the separated solid product, the residue washed with alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow plates, m. p. 201°-203°. (Found: N, 17·12, C₂₂H₂₀O₂N₂S, requires N, 17·23 per cent.).

5-Phenyl-2-thiol-1-allyl-1:3:4-triazole disulphide.—The benzylidene-4 allylthiosemicarbazone was oxidised as before. The separated solid was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m. p. 90°. (Found: N, 19·63. C₂₂H₂₀N₂S₂, requires N, 19·44 per cent.).

5-m-Nitrophenyl-1-allyl-1:3:4-triazole.—It was prepared either by oxidising the *m*-nitrobenzylidene-4-allylthiosemicarbazone with excess of peroxide or by oxidising the triazole disulphide with the same reagent. The product so obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m. p. 194°-195°. (Found: N, 24·51. C₁₁H₁₀O₂N₄, requires N, 24·35 per cent.).

5-Phenyl-1-p-tolyl-2-thiol-1:3:4-triazole disulphide.—Benzylidene-4-*p*-tolylthiosemicarbazone was suspended in water and the oxidising agent added with shaking. On heating the mixture a vigorous reaction began with frothing. The mixture was heated for 20 mins., cooled and filtered. Crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow rectangles it melts at 155°-156°. (Found: S, 12·39. C₂₀H₁₈N₂S₂, requires S, 12·03 per cent.).

5-Phenyl-1-ethyl-2-thiol-1:3:4-triazole disulphide.—It was obtained from benzylidene-4-ethylthiosemicarbazone (m. p. 138°) in alcoholic suspension. The carbazone gradually went into solution on heating. From the clear solution on cooling the disulphide separated in yellow crystals, m. p. 88°. (Found: N, 20·89. C₁₆H₂₀N₂S₂, requires N, 20·59 per cent.).

1:5-Diphenyl-2-thiol-1:3:4-triazole disulphide.—It was obtained from benzylidene-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone by oxidation as before. On heating the carbazone gradually dissolved and after heating for about 10 mins. the solution was cooled when the disulphide separated as a crystalline product. This was crystallised from acetic acid in white needles. It shrinks at 186° and melts at 232° with decomposition. (Found: N, 17·82. C₂₈H₂₀N₂S₂, requires N, 16·66 per cent.).

5-m-Nitrophenyl-2-thiol-1-allyl-1:3:4-triazole disulphide.—The *m*-nitrobenzylidene-4-allylthiosemicarbazone was oxidised in alcoholic suspension. The mixture was heated under reflux when the

reaction commenced with effervescence and the carbazone went into solution and after a few minutes the oxidation product separated as a crystalline solid. This was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates. It shrinks at 144° and melts at 173°. (Found: N, 21·28. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 21·46 per cent.).

Oxidation of Acetone Thiosemicarbazones with Hydrogen Peroxide.

2:5-Diacetonehydrazido-1:3:4-thiodiazole

The acetone-thiosemicarbazone was dissolved in alcohol and hydrogen peroxide was slowly added. The reaction began at once with evolution of heat. The solution was filtered from sulphur that separated out after heating the mixture for about 10 mins. and the crystals obtained on cooling the filtrate were recrystallised from alcohol in white rectangles, m. p. 260° with decomposition. (Found: S, 14·65. $C_6H_{14}N_4S$ requires S, 14·16 per cent.).

Heated with strong hydrochloric acid the above thiodiazole gradually dissolved after about one hour. The solution was filtered and concentrated; on cooling crystals of a hydrochloride separated, m. p. 157° with decomposition, which on analysis was found to be hydrazine hydrochloride.

2:5-Diacetonehydrazide-3:4-diphenyl-1:3:1-thiodiazole.

Acetone-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone (m. p. 125°) was covered with alcohol and the peroxide was slowly added, the mixture being cooled in ice water during addition. The reaction began immediately and the solid went into solution and after a few seconds a red crystalline product separated. This was filtered and crystallised from alcohol in golden yellow plates, m. p. 168° with decomposition. (Found: N, 22·13. $C_{10}H_{11}N_4S$ requires N, 22·13 per cent.).

The thiodiazole was decomposed by heating with strong hydrochloric acid. The solution was filtered, concentrated and from the solution hydrazine hydrochloride separated out.

2:5-Diacetonhydrazido-3:4-di-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazole.

Acetone-4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazone (m. p. 139°) was oxidised as before in aqueous suspension. On heating the mixture an oily substance separated which solidified after cooling. Crystallised from methyl alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal it separates in red prisms, m. p. 124°. (Found: N, 20.81. C₁₂H₁₆N₂S requires N, 20.69 per cent.).

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